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Assessing the Role of the SHARED GREEN DEAL Experiments in Achieving Zero Pollution Goals

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Executive summary

This report synthesizes the key findings from a secondary analysis of the Horizon Europe SHARED GREEN DEAL project, examining how the concept of Zero Pollution intersects with the insights and activities of six thematic social experiment streams. While pollution is not the primary focus of the project, this analysis explores how experimental practices in areas such as energy, circular economy, construction, mobility, food systems, and biodiversity can foster pollution reduction as a co-benefit of social innovation and behavioural change.

Findings show that local participation is crucial for addressing pollution across multiple domains – including air, water, soil, noise, and material waste. Through methods such as Study Circles, Urban Mobility Labs, and Community Energy Workshops, participants developed stronger awareness of pollution’s impacts on health and ecosystems, while co-creating locally grounded responses. These approaches proved effective in translating abstract environmental goals into everyday actions, particularly when pollution was linked to visible or lived experiences.

However, significant barriers remain. Many initiatives operated within fragmented policy landscapes, with limited integration between environmental and sectoral regulations. Insufficient access to data, funding, and institutional support hindered their capacity to scale or influence decision-making. In some cases, pollution was addressed only indirectly, or lacked consistent framing in project design and communication. Additionally, groups—such as low-income households and rural communities—often lacked the resources or infrastructure to participate in or benefit from pollution-reduction efforts.

The report underscores the importance of multi-level coordination. At the local level, participatory learning and grassroots innovation must be supported through education, and inclusive planning. At the regional and national levels, aligning policies across sectors—especially agriculture, energy, mobility, and food systems—is essential to overcome contradictions and improve regulatory coherence. Funding instruments and pollution monitoring systems must also be adapted to track the contributions of small-scale actors. At the EU and international levels, stronger policy harmonisation and investment in transdisciplinary models are required to connect social innovation with measurable environmental outcomes. Supporting social-ecological innovations that combine technological solutions with community empowerment will be key to achieving systemic change in regards to zero pollution.

In conclusion, while pollution was not the primary focus of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, its social experiments demonstrate promising entry points for reducing pollution through inclusive, place-based approaches. To fully realise the potential of these approaches, policies must address structural gaps and embed pollution goals with monitoring mechanisms more explicitly into climate, health, and social equity agendas. A just and resilient transition toward the EU’s 2050 vision of a pollution-free environment will require coordinated action across all levels of governance – rooted in equity, participation, and systemic thinking.

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1. Introduction

1.1. SHARED GREEN DEAL project

This report presents insights from the **SHARED GREEN DEAL** project (Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal) which is part of the Horizon 2020 programme. The SHARED GREEN DEAL project aligns with the overarching aims of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019) policy programme to achieve climate neutrality and a toxic-free environment by 2050. Its core mission is to foster behavioural, social, and cultural transformations across Europe that are aligned with the strategic priorities of the European Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. The focus of this secondary analysis is to distill key insights across the six thematic SHARED GREEN DEAL streams, specifically highlighting two **cross-cutting priorities** of the European Green Deal: **climate action** and **zero pollution**. The report includes a policy overview, followed by thematic insights derived from the respective workstreams (Section 2). These are complemented by a set of cross-cutting recommendations (Section 3) and concluding reflections that synthesize key findings and implications (Section 4).

At the core of SHARED GREEN DEAL are six thematic streams aligned with key Green Deal priorities: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Biodiversity Preservation. SHARED GREEN DEAL implemented social experiments across different EU Member States and affiliated countries, designed to generate lessons for one of the six priority topics. Rooted in transdisciplinary action research, these experiments combine practical and academic knowledge to drive change through hands-on learning, pilots, and grass-roots innovation.

The experiment streams were implemented in four European locations each between April 2023 and June 2024, spanning 17 countries (see Figure 1.1). A total of 24 social experiments have been delivered across different member states and affiliated countries, working with local municipalities and not-for-profit organisations. Emphasizing two-way dialogue and inclusive participation, local NGOs and public authorities led the initiatives, ensuring alignment with local contexts and existing networks.

Figure 1.1. Map of the locations of the 24 SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments across Europe (Kovács et al., 2024).

The **Clean Energy** experiment stream explored how community visioning can support climate action through just, inclusive energy transitions. Four local partners were selected to work on this theme from Ærø (Denmark), Granada (Spain), Belchatów (Poland), and Essex (UK). Social experiments were launched in all four locations to co-create local visions for sustainable energy futures. Although only three of the experiments were brought to completion, they nevertheless provided valuable lessons on connecting local knowledge with broader climate goals, and on fostering relationships, awareness, and capacity-building among stakeholders.

The **Circular Economy** experiment stream focused on supporting business innovation through the establishment of Local Accelerator Hubs (LAHs) in Portugal, Cyprus, Slovenia, and France. These

LAHs served as physical and digital platforms for co-creation, knowledge sharing, and collaboration among local stakeholders including businesses, authorities, and civil society. The aim was to promote circular business models that reduce waste, regenerate resources, and align with EU climate and sustainability goals. The experiments contributed to building local capacity, embedding circular practices in communities, and linking local action to European frameworks such as the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) under the European Green Deal.

The **Efficient Renovations** experiment stream addressed a critical area of climate action by targeting emissions reductions in the building sector—one of the EU’s key priorities for achieving climate neutrality. This stream explored how social, technical, and policy factors intersect in the context of housing renovation. Through the creation of Knowledge Networks in four European locations—Hungary, Ireland, Spain, and Lithuania—citizens and professionals were brought together to share know-how, build capacity, and co-develop solutions. These networks helped foster practical understanding and increased motivation for energy-efficient retrofits.

The **Sustainable Mobility** experiment stream focused on sustainable mobility, especially within schools by developing context-specific mobility strategies within Urban Mobility Labs. Urban Mobility Labs were developed within schools in four European cities – Braga (Portugal), Galway (Ireland), Panevezys (Lithuania), and Sofia (Bulgaria) and involved youth and stakeholders including teachers, parents and school administrators. The aim of the initiatives, in which particular focus was given to involving young people, was to promote sustainable mobility in schools, infrastructure improvements, and mobility policies. Such co-creative participation processes have proven effective in raising awareness and encouraging sustainable transportation.

The **Sustainable Food** experiment stream explored how agroecology and local food systems can support climate action and sustainability goals. Four social experiments were conducted in Italy, Slovakia, Sweden, and the Netherlands, each applying the transition arena approach—a collaborative process that brings together local actors to co-create visions and strategies for transformation. These initiatives aimed to demonstrate how local practices, rooted in community values and sustainability principles, can drive system-level change in the food system. While each initiative successfully developed locally relevant solutions, they also revealed the need for stronger support and coordination beyond the local level to achieve broader climate impacts.

The **Preserving Biodiversity** experiment stream investigated the various values people place on biodiversity in both rural and urban settings. To achieve this, Study Circles were implemented – a non-formal community learning method – in four locations: Slovenia, Greece, Sweden, and Ireland. Groups of adults met monthly as part of this social experiment, with the expectation that the outcomes will lead to transformative changes in how participants value biodiversity, ultimately aiding in efforts to combat biodiversity loss as part of the broader EU Green Deal agenda.

A summarised overview with further information on each experiment site, the methodological approaches as well as the target groups can be found in Table A1.1, in the Appendix.

1.2. Introducing this report

This report contributes to the evolving policy discourse on Zero Pollution by examining how socially driven forms of innovation can inform and complement existing environmental governance in regards to zero pollution ambitions. Drawing on a secondary analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, it explores how insights from participatory experiments – though not initially focused on pollution – can support a more systemic and inclusive transition toward a pollution-free Europe.

The report's objective is not to replicate technical assessments of pollution sources or trends, but to foreground the social, behavioural, and institutional dimensions that are often underrepresented in environmental policymaking. It situates the findings of the SHARED GREEN DEAL within the broader strategic aims of the EU's Zero Pollution Action Plan, reflecting critically on how bottom-up initiatives may help close persistent policy and implementation gaps—particularly in relation to equity, participation, and local relevance.

To this end, the report begins with an overview of the international and European policy context for Zero Pollution, identifying key legislative frameworks and structural challenges, with a particular emphasis on social inclusion. It then examines how pollution-related dynamics were addressed across the six thematic streams of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project – ranging from clean energy, efficient renovations, and sustainable mobility to circular economy, food systems, and biodiversity preservation. Building on these insights, the report develops a series of multi-level policy recommendations aimed at improving alignment between innovation and institutional reform. It concludes with a reflection on the enabling conditions required to advance Zero Pollution goals in ways that are not only environmentally effective, but also socially just and contextually grounded.

In doing so, the report highlights the importance of integrating diverse knowledge systems and participatory approaches into pollution governance—underscoring that lasting progress towards Zero Pollution will depend as much on inclusive social processes as on regulatory enforcement or technological advancement.

1.3. Data sources

This report draws upon insights and recommendations from six individual reports on each social experiment stream (Beers et al. 2025, Foulds et al. 2025, Gray et al. 2025a, Haufe and Tönkö 2025, Ruiz et al. 2025, Šmid Hribar et al. 2025a) (see also Table A1.2 in the appendix) as well as internal appendices that included reflections on implications of each experiment stream to Climate Action and Zero Pollution (guiding questions are provided in Box 1.2). The above mentioned reports and internal appendices analysed the 24 social experiments, including summaries of their design and participant numbers. These elements were key inputs for the current analysis, alongside the SHARED GREEN DEAL Case Study Guides (Kovács et al. 2024) and the SHARED GREEN DEAL European policies analysis for policy contextualization. However, as these materials often contained only limited reflection on climate action and zero pollution, since these issues were not explicitly addressed during the social experiments, the authors of this report complemented them with additional information drawn from existing policy reports and published literature.

In parallel with the Analysis Reports on Climate Action (Šmid Hribar et al. 2025b) and Zero Pollution, respectively, a complementary set of documents provide secondary analyses of the social experiments data across five cross-cutting Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) priority themes: (i) Gender and diversity (Aggeli et al. 2025), (ii) Justice, Vulnerabilities and Inequalities (Bharucha

2025), (iii) Societal Challenges (post-COVID-19) (Truninger et al. 2025), (iv) Governance agendas, conventions and framings (Gray et al. 2025b), (v) Geographic differences and evolutions across time (Nieboer et al. 2025). These are available on the project's website. Other resources related to the implementation and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreen-deal.eu.

Box 1.3. Guiding questions to stimulate reflection on implications of experiment streams to Zero Pollution.

- In what ways did your experiment approach support progress toward the Zero Pollution targets at local, regional, national and/or international levels? Please try to briefly describe at least one concrete action.
- How particular pollution related policy contexts (policy gaps and regulatory barriers or supportive policy framework) in your geographic locations affected your experiment and its outcome?
- How did your experiment approach create opportunities for regional collaboration and knowledge-sharing to drive zero pollution efforts?
- How your experiment approach could foster transformative change and systemic solutions to zero pollution challenges?
- The key difficulties/limitations in terms of promoting zero pollution; and how future experiments might better mitigate them?

Building on these insights, the report develops a series of multi-level policy recommendations aimed at improving alignment between basic innovation and institutional reform. It concludes with a reflection on the enabling conditions required to advance Zero Pollution goals in ways that are not only environmentally effective but also socially just and contextually grounded. In doing so, the report highlights the importance of integrating diverse knowledge systems and participatory approaches into zero pollution governance, underscoring that lasting progress towards a pollution-free Europe by 2050 will depend as much on inclusive social processes as on regulatory enforcement or technological advancements.

Organised in *Experiences and lessons learnt*, *Challenges and Limitations* and *Actions needed*, the insights from this report highlight how these barriers for zero pollution manifest and how they can be better tackled.

2. Policy overview on Zero Pollution

Pollution poses serious threats to human health, ecosystems, and biodiversity. Acting now to prevent and reduce pollution is essential to safeguarding environmental and societal well-being. **Zero Pollution** encompasses all actions aimed at minimizing harmful emissions and pollutants to levels that are no longer considered detrimental to the environment and all its inhabitants, including humans.

This ambition involves two complementary approaches:

Pollution prevention: reducing emissions and waste at the source to stop new pollution from occurring, and

Pollution remediation: restoring ecosystems and environments already damaged by pollutants to ensure long-term resilience and recovery.

This chapter outlines the policy context for the EU's Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP), from a global outline of key international policy frameworks, moving through the EU's policy landscape, and concluding with an analysis of policy gaps—particularly in relation to social inclusion and equity.

2.1. Global Context: International policies and legislative frameworks

Pollution, in its various forms—chemical, biological, waste, particulate, noise, thermal and light-related — affects different environments, posing severe environmental and health risks. Global initiatives addressing pollution have been established through multilateral agreements and international frameworks.

A landmark event took place in 1972 when the **United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)** was established following the Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment, positioning UNEP as the primary global body responsible for coordinating pollution-reduction initiatives (United Nations Environment Programme, 1972). This initiative was further strengthened by the **Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal**, which was adopted in 1989 and entered into force in 1993. This convention aims to regulate the cross-border movement of hazardous waste and mitigate associated environmental risks.

Further international agreements addressing pollution include the **Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants** (Secretariat of the Stockholm Convention, 2025), adopted in 2001, which seeks to limit the production and use of hazardous organic chemicals, and the **Minamata Convention on Mercury** (United Nations Environment Programme, 2013), which was adopted in 2013 to control mercury emissions and protect both human health and the environment. Although the **Paris Agreement** (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2015) primarily targets climate change, it indirectly supports pollution reduction by curbing the use of fossil fuels—a major source of air pollution.

The **United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)**, adopted in 1982 (United Nations, 1982), plays a crucial role in addressing marine pollution by establishing a legal framework for ocean

governance, including regulations on pollution from land-based sources, ships, and seabed activities. Additionally, the **UNECE Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution** (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, 1979) provides a framework for international cooperation to address air pollution that crosses national borders, aiming to reduce harmful emissions and their environmental impacts. Another significant initiative is the Global Program of Action for the Protection of the **Marine Environment from Land-based Activities (GPA)**¹, established in 1995, which seeks to prevent the degradation of marine ecosystems by controlling land-based sources of pollution such as sewage, agricultural runoff, and industrial discharges.

In addition to these legally binding agreements, in the 2015, **UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** reinforce global commitments to pollution mitigation. Goals directly related to pollution include Goal 3 (Good Health and Well-being), Goal 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). These objectives align with the 2019 UN Resolution on Air Pollution, which emphasizes the urgency of reducing pollution-related mortality and environmental degradation.

Despite these compelling and multiplex international legislative and policy frameworks, pollution persists due to a complex interplay of economic, political and social factors, compounded by weak and inconsistent enforcement. Pollution levels continue to threaten human health and the environment, highlighting the persistent gap between international commitments and their national, regional and local practical implementation.

2.2. The EU Zero Pollution Policy Framework

The European Union has developed a comprehensive policy framework to achieve its zero pollution ambition, integrating various strategies and legislative measures across multiple sectors. Central to the EU's efforts is the **Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP)**, adopted in May 2021 as part of the **European Green Deal**. The ZPAP sets a 2050 vision to reduce air, water, and soil pollution to levels no longer harmful to health and natural ecosystems, aiming for a pollution-free environment. To expedite progress, the plan outlines key 2030 targets, including improving air quality to reduce the number of premature deaths caused by air pollution by 55%, enhancing water quality by reducing waste, plastic litter at sea by 50%, and microplastics released into the environment by 30%, and improving soil quality by reducing nutrient losses and chemical pesticide use by 50% (European Commission, 2021).

Several legislative and policy instruments underlie the EU's Zero Pollution efforts. **The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** plays a crucial role in addressing priority pollutants such as plastics and microplastics, underwater noise, hazardous chemicals (i.e. heavy metals, POPs, pesticides, nutrients, etc.), setting environmental targets and requiring Member States to establish monitoring and control programs (European Commission, 2023a). **The Ambient Air Quality Directive** has been revised to align EU air quality standards more closely with World Health Organization guidelines, setting interim 2030 targets and positioning the EU on a trajectory to achieve zero pollution for air by 2050 (European Commission, 2023b). **The Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive**, updated in 2022, mandates more effective wastewater treatment to ensure cleaner rivers, lakes, and seas across Europe (European Commission, 2022). **The Water Framework Directive** establishes a framework for protecting inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater, aiming to prevent further deterioration and protect aquatic ecosystems.

¹ United Nations Environment Programme, 1995.

The **Circular Economy Action Plan**, adopted in March 2020 is also central to the EU's pollution-reduction ambitions. It focuses on waste reduction and sustainable resource use, aiming to decouple economic growth from resource consumption by keeping materials in the economy for as long as possible (European Commission, 2020). In line with the EU's commitment to clean mobility, the EU has also mandated that all new cars and vans sold from 2035 must emit zero carbon dioxide (Council of the EU, 2023). Despite some recent extensions to compliance deadlines for intermediate targets, the principal goals for 2025, 2030, and 2035 remain unchanged.

The **Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability**, adopted in 2020, is a key component of the EU's zero pollution ambition, designed to protect citizens and the environment from hazardous chemicals while promoting innovation in safer alternatives. The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability complements and reinforces REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals), which has been the cornerstone of EU chemical regulation since 2007. REACH requires companies to provide information on the properties and safe use of chemicals, ensuring they are properly assessed and that any risks to human health or the environment are effectively managed. The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability further strengthens the objectives of REACH by enhancing the regulation of hazardous chemicals and promoting safer alternatives.

Alongside regulatory measures, financial and social mechanisms are in place to ensure a just and equitable transition. To ensure social equity in pollution reduction, the **Just Transition Mechanism (JTM)** has been implemented to support workers and regions historically dependent on pollution-intensive industries, to attempt to prevent economic marginalization. What is more, the **Social Climate Fund** provides financial assistance to vulnerable households disproportionately affected by environmental policies, ensuring a fair distribution of the economic burdens of pollution control measures.

The direction of EU pollution-reduction action policy under the current Commission (2024-2029) remains uncertain. However, the **Competitiveness Compass**, released in January 2025 (Environmental Commission, 2025; European Environmental Bureau, 2025), offers some indications of forthcoming initiatives. Key proposed measures include the Clean Industrial Deal, an Action Plan on Affordable Energy, a Sustainable Transport Plan, a High-Speed Rail Plan, a Vision for Agriculture and Food, a Circular Economy Act, and revisions to environmental regulations to align with competitiveness objectives (European Commission, 2025).

2.3. Policy Gaps and Structural Challenges for achieving Zero Pollution

Despite considerable progress, several gaps continue to challenge the EU's pollution-reduction efforts. Enforcement remains inconsistent across Member States, with significant discrepancies in the implementation of industrial emissions controls and water quality regulations. Differences between Western and Eastern European nations, in particular, create an uneven playing field in pollution governance (European Environment Agency, 2024a).

Contradictions within EU policy frameworks further undermine pollution reduction efforts. Subsidies for pollution-intensive industries, particularly in agriculture and transport, continue to coexist alongside ambitious pollution-reduction targets, limiting overall policy coherence (WWF, 2025). The economic burden of compliance with pollution regulations remains a significant issue, particularly for low-income and marginalized communities, who often experience the highest levels of pollution exposure, yet social protections and financial assistance remain insufficient,

with concerns over the affordability of pollution-reduction technologies and compliance costs for businesses (European Environmental Bureau, 2023). While financial assistance mechanisms exist, support remains insufficient to address the full scale of environmental inequality.

Emission reductions, though progressing, are not on track to meet 2030 targets. A recent report by the European Environment Agency (European Environment Agency, 2024b) found that while greenhouse gas emissions in the EU fell by 8% in 2023, current policies indicate only a 43% reduction by 2030—falling short of the original 55% target. Further action is needed to bridge this gap, particularly through stricter enforcement and greater investment in pollution-free technologies. Moreover, current pollution monitoring frameworks require further standardization and real-time tracking capabilities to enhance compliance and progress assessment towards zero pollution targets (European Environment Agency, 2024a).

Public engagement with pollution policies remains another area of concern. The limited integration of behavioural, social, and cultural insights in environmental policymaking has contributed to weak public participation in pollution-reduction efforts. Research suggests that inclusive policy-making processes are needed to better address socio-economic disparities and ensure that local populations actively participate in pollution mitigation strategies (Urios et al., 2022). While the ZPAP establishes an ambitious and necessary framework for tackling pollution, significant gaps persist in enforcement, social equity considerations, and policy coherence. Addressing these challenges requires stronger integration of social sciences' perspectives, enhanced public engagement, and more effective monitoring mechanisms to ensure the EU's transition towards a pollution-free environment is not only effective but also socially and economically just.

3. SHARED GREEN DEAL Stream Insights on Zero Pollution

This chapter explores how local communities, citizens, and a wide range of stakeholders can contribute to reducing pollution and advancing environmental health, drawing on the social experiments conducted across the six SHARED GREEN DEAL thematic streams: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Biodiversity Preservation. The analysis highlights how grassroots engagement, inclusive governance, and behavioral shifts in daily life can support pollution reduction across domains—whether through low-emission mobility, sustainable agriculture, material reuse, or ecological restoration. By identifying key challenges and actionable lessons, this chapter offers insights into how collaborative, multi-level strategies can promote healthier environments and drive progress toward a pollution-free Europe.

The six thematic streams of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project address pollution in diverse but complementary ways—ranging from reducing transport-related emissions (air) to minimizing pesticide runoff (water and soil) and limiting construction waste (material pollution). These experiments, though not originally designed with Zero Pollution as a primary objective, reveal how integrated, community-based action can contribute meaningfully to achieve the EU's Zero Pollution targets.

3.1. Clean Energy

Experiences and Lessons Learned

The Clean Energy social experiments emphasized the power of community visioning workshops in linking local energy systems to environmental health promotion and pollution reduction. By integrating pollution-related data into discussions, participants could see the tangible health and ecological impacts of fossil fuel use, motivating engagement in renewable energy initiatives and energy communities. In some communities, pollution served as a compelling entry point for clean energy conversations, especially when aligned with lived experiences of environmental degradation. However, the presence of polluting industries that provide economic stability complicates these transitions. In regions like Bełchatów, economic dependence on coal triggered resistance and required nuanced, just transition frameworks.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite these gains, pollution was not consistently integrated into Clean Energy dialogues. Participants often perceived energy transition as an economic or technological issue, not one linked to environmental health. Furthermore, in some heavily industrialized areas, dependence on coal created deep tensions—pollution was acknowledged, but concerns about employment dominated. This trade-off limited the perceived legitimacy of anti-pollution arguments. A lack of policy tools to tie clean energy adoption to direct pollution benefits (e.g., air quality incentives) further weakened the connection. Additionally, community efforts struggled to access pollution data at sufficient granularity or in real time, hampering localized action.

Actions Needed

- Embedding pollution-related narratives into community visioning to strengthen participation and ownership.
- Highlighting co-benefits for health, wellbeing and environmental quality when designing local engagement processes.
- Ensuring local transition plans integrate pollution reduction as a central goal, not just a side-effect of clean energy.
- Decentralized renewable energy initiatives must be supported to ensure communities' accessibility and inclusiveness.
- Fostering cross-sector collaboration (e.g. health, housing, energy) to link zero pollution goals with broader social outcomes.

3.2. Circular Economy

Experiences and Lessons Learned

The Circular Economy stream illustrated that reducing material waste through reuse, repair, and sustainable design has direct implications for reducing both solid waste and associated emissions. The Local Accelerator Hubs (dedicated collaborative spaces) helped businesses identify pollution hotspots in their operations—such as chemical runoff, packaging waste, and emissions from production processes—and co-design alternatives. In France, some hubs tracked reductions in single-use plastics and monitored local air quality improvements near manufacturing zones. These bottom-up innovations made pollution reduction more visible as both an economic and environmental opportunity.

Challenges and Limitations

One key limitation was the absence of standardized tools to quantify pollution reductions across hubs, making it hard to benchmark or communicate success. SMEs in Portugal and Cyprus often lacked the capacity to assess environmental externalities or adopt cleaner technologies without external support. Cultural resistance to using second-hand or repurposed materials also persisted in some communities, reducing uptake. Moreover, while pollution reduction was a by-product of circularity, it was rarely framed as a central goal, which weakened buy-in from actors who were not already sustainability-minded. Enforcement of pollution-related regulations also varied widely by region, creating an inconsistent incentives' landscape.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen regulatory frameworks, introduce incentives for circular practices, and promote their coherence across the EU.
- Launch targeted support programs for SMEs, including financial aid and technical training.
- Promote circularity through education campaigns to change public perceptions and behavior.

- Develop and implement standardized indicators for measuring circular economy impacts on pollution. Include quantified impacts (even rough estimates) on waste or emissions, if available.
- Elaborate on how waste avoidance = pollution prevention, drawing clearer distinctions between upstream (design) vs. downstream (waste) efforts.
- Foster regional cooperation and best practice exchange through transnational networks.

3.3. Efficient Renovations

Experiences and Lessons Learned

The social experiments in building renovation showed that improvements in building energy performance—such as better insulation, cleaner heating, and material reuse—can indirectly reduce indoor and urban pollution. Participants in Knowledge Networks began to make connections between air quality (both indoor and neighborhood-level) and building design. In Hungary and Lithuania, residents were surprised to learn how certain heating methods (like burning solid fuels) contributed to both indoor particulate matter and wider air pollution. The shared learning approach increased awareness of the health and environmental risks of energy inefficient homes.

Challenges and Limitations

Pollution concerns were often treated as secondary to cost savings or energy efficiency. Many renovation actors (contractors, homeowners) lacked knowledge of how construction materials (e.g., paints, insulation) contribute to indoor air pollution or waste streams. Financial and bureaucratic barriers prevented wider uptake of low-emission materials or renovation methods. For example, builders were more likely to choose cheaper but more polluting products due to market availability. In some rural areas, DIY renovations perpetuated unsafe practices like burning construction waste or using outdated insulation materials with harmful chemicals. There was also no mechanism in place to measure post-renovation pollution levels, limiting feedback.

Actions Needed

- Embed pollution considerations into energy efficiency guidelines and renovation funding schemes.
- Specify conditions/criteria contributing to indoor pollution (e.g., materials off-gassing, mold, heating fuels) and how retrofits improve air quality or reduce emissions. Note if residents become more aware of indoor pollutants through their engagement in the monitoring.
- Provide contractor training and homeowner education on sustainable renovation choices.
- Support research and development in low-emission building materials.
- Incentivize material reuse and low-waste construction practices.
- Integrate pollution reduction metrics into building certification and energy labeling systems.

3.4. Sustainable Mobility

Experiences and Lessons Learned

The Urban Mobility Labs created space for communities—especially youth—to understand how transport choices affect pollution. By promoting walking, cycling, and public transport, the labs reduced car dependency and generated indirect benefits such as improved air quality around schools. In Braga and Galway, student-led campaigns emphasized the links between vehicle emissions and respiratory health, encouraging modal shifts. The Urban Mobility Labs also addressed noise and visual pollution by promoting more livable urban environments. Co-creation led to stronger local ownership of mobility plans and helped normalize sustainable modes.

Challenges and Limitations

Infrastructure remained a critical barrier. In several sites, inadequate sidewalks, poor cycling networks, and unsafe crossings undermined efforts to reduce transport pollution. Participants frequently cited traffic congestion and poor public transport as disincentives. The Labs had limited influence on regional or national transport systems, which continue to prioritize car-centric planning. Long-standing habits and parental concerns also hindered shifts in behavior. Importantly, there was limited capacity to monitor pollution levels before and after interventions, which weakened the Urban Mobility Labs' ability to demonstrate impact and advocate for further investment.

Actions Needed

- Scale Urban Mobility Labs and institutionalize them within educational systems.
- Invest in pedestrian and cycling infrastructure.
- Provide examples of emissions data, even estimated (e.g., “walking buses reduced estimated CO₂ by X%” or “shift to biking lowered particulate exposure at school entrances”).
- Highlight any policy dialogue triggered on traffic or transport emissions.
- Strengthen partnerships between schools and local authorities to implement mobility reforms.
- Run targeted campaigns on pollution and health impacts of transport.
- Advocate for stronger alignment between local innovation and national transport planning.

3.5. Sustainable Food

Experiences and Lessons Learned

Agroecological approaches demonstrated clear benefits for pollution reduction—through lower pesticide use, improved soil health, and reduced food transport emissions. The Transition Arena

processes and approach enabled communities to explore how local food production could limit nutrient runoff and chemical inputs, thereby protecting waterways and soil. In Italy and Sweden, composting and food waste education helped close nutrient loops and reduce landfill contributions. In Slovakia, local actors became aware of how food choices (e.g., packaged imports) were linked to pollution footprints, especially plastic waste and transport emissions.

Challenges and Limitations

Widespread structural constraints limited the food initiatives' ability to fully deliver on pollution goals. Industrial agriculture, with its heavy use of synthetic inputs and fossil-fuel-based logistics, remained the dominant model. Many agroecological initiatives lacked access to markets or subsidies that reward low-pollution practices. Food system fragmentation and siloed policy frameworks (e.g., separate regulations for agriculture, environment, and health) made integrated action difficult. Local efforts often did not have the political weight to challenge unsustainable procurement practices, such as schools sourcing from centralized, high-emission supply chains. Pollution impacts were also rarely communicated in consumer-facing campaigns, limiting awareness.

Actions Needed

- Enhance subsidies and support for regenerative and organic farming.
- Promote farm-to-fork models and reduce food transport emissions.
- Better integrate pollution sources from food systems (fertilizers, runoff, transport emissions).
- Expand food waste composting and redistribution infrastructure.
- Specifically frame local agroecological practices as pollution-reducing (e.g., composting, fewer pesticides).
- Improve consumer education through experiential programs and labeling reforms.
- Facilitate trans-local networks to elevate local voices and scale best practices.

3.6. Preserving Biodiversity

Experiences and Lessons Learned

Study Circles proved highly effective in linking biodiversity preservation to pollution reduction. These non-formal learning spaces enabled community members to explore how biodiversity loss intersects with pollution, particularly through local projects like urban community gardens, sustainable agriculture, and reforestation efforts. Transformative learning emerged as a significant process, with participants reporting paradigm shifts through “disorienting dilemmas” that prompted reflection on personal and communal environmental practices. The combination of sustainable agricultural practices and localized ecological restoration led to tangible environmental improvements. For example, reduced pesticide use and waste minimization were direct outcomes of improved community understanding of biodiversity's role in pollution control. Community engagement played a central role, making biodiversity issues more relatable and actionable for local populations.

Challenges and Limitations

One key challenge was regional disparity in pollution and biodiversity policy enforcement. While countries like Ireland supported sustainable agriculture through policy alignment, others lacked coherent strategies, creating fragmented efforts. There was also a limited public awareness of the interconnectedness of biodiversity and pollution, which hindered broader societal uptake. Economic barriers presented another hurdle. Many farmers and landowners were hesitant to adopt biodiversity-friendly practices without clear financial incentives or technical support. Additionally, the communication gap among policymakers, practitioners, and citizens meant that the interdependence between biodiversity and pollution control was often poorly articulated.

Actions Needed

- Flesh out how biodiversity loss results from pollution and, conversely, how improved ecosystems (like urban greening) help mitigate it.
- National and regional policies need to be aligned to uniformly support biodiversity-positive pollution reduction measures.
- Biodiversity and pollution awareness should be integrated into school curricula and community education initiatives.
- Financial and technical support must be expanded for farmers to adopt sustainable practices.
- Initiatives like urban gardens and reforestation projects should be scaled and interconnected to form collaborative networks.
- Mechanisms for cross-sector knowledge sharing and partnerships must be established, linking scientists, communities, and policymakers.

4. Recommendations for Multi-Level Action on Zero Pollution

Achieving the EU Zero Pollution Action Plan requires coherent and coordinated action across all governance levels, from local initiatives to EU-wide policy frameworks. Yet, as the policy analysis reveals, persistent gaps in enforcement, coherence, monitoring, and social equity continue to undermine progress. The experiences across clean energy, circular economy, building renovations, mobility, food systems, and biodiversity show that these structural issues play out at the local level, where promising initiatives often confront fragmented regulations, insufficient financial support, and contradictory policy signals. Addressing these barriers demands integrated solutions that link EU ambitions with local realities.

At the **local level**, pollution reduction efforts must move beyond treating environmental and human health as a secondary co-benefit and instead place it at the center of community education, planning, and innovation. Social experiments such as Study Circles, Urban Mobility Labs, and Community Energy Workshops demonstrated that behavioral change and local ownership emerge when communities can connect abstract policy goals to lived experiences, health outcomes, and tangible environmental improvements. Yet local actors frequently lacked access to real-time pollution data or supportive regulatory tools to make these connections meaningful. Municipalities should therefore embed pollution awareness into urban planning, school curricula, and public health campaigns, while EU and national institutions must provide the technical infrastructure—such as standardized monitoring systems—that the policy analysis identified as currently missing. This would help close the gap between policy ambition and local implementation capacity, allowing communities to track and demonstrate progress toward zero-pollution objectives.

At the **regional and national levels**, policy coherence and infrastructure investment are essential to overcome structural contradictions such as ongoing subsidies for pollution-intensive sectors. These inconsistencies, directly undermine local transitions, as seen in regions economically dependent on coal or industrial agriculture. National governments must integrate pollution reduction metrics into energy transition plans, building renovation schemes, food system reforms, and transport strategies, ensuring that environmental, economic, and social objectives reinforce rather than compete with one another. Investments in cycling networks, public transport, renewable energy access, composting facilities, and circular economy logistics should be scaled up to make low-pollution choices both viable and attractive. At the same time, financial and technical assistance for farmers, SMEs, and low-income households must be expanded to prevent the environmental inequalities identified in the policy analysis from deepening as transition policies advance.

At the **EU and international levels**, stronger strategic alignment and long-term investment are needed to ensure consistency, equity, and scalability. The policy chapter highlights how fragmented enforcement and insufficient integration of behavioral and social dimensions limit current efforts. The EU should therefore align zero pollution objectives across all Green Deal pillars, ensuring that biodiversity restoration, climate neutrality, and circular economy policies work in synergy rather than isolation. Funding programs must prioritize integrated approaches that combine technological innovation with social engagement and measurable environmental outcomes, rewarding projects that demonstrate clear reductions in emissions, pollution exposure, or ecosystem degradation. Transnational knowledge-sharing platforms would help address the uneven implementation

revealed in the policy analysis by enabling cities, regions, and civil society actors to exchange tools, data, and best practices across borders. Finally, embedding environmental justice principles into all zero-pollution policies would help ensure that the economic and health benefits of cleaner environments are distributed fairly, particularly in communities currently facing both high pollution exposure and limited access to transition resources.

By directly addressing the enforcement gaps, policy contradictions, monitoring weaknesses, and equity challenges outlined in the policy analysis, these recommendations aim to transform the EU's zero-pollution ambition from a largely top-down legislative framework into a systemic, community-centered, and measurable transition that delivers tangible health and environmental benefits across all member states.

Table 4.1. Recommendations for Action: From Local to EU Level – A Multi-Level Approach to Zero Pollution.

Governance Level	Key Priorities	Suggested Actions / Methods	Inspirational Examples	Key actors
Local	Empower communities Promote behavior change	Participatory education Co-creation approaches Integration in schools urban planning, and public health	Study Circles Urban Mobility Labs Community Energy Workshops	Municipal / city governments Schools and educational institutions NGOs
Regional / National	Align policies Expand support mechanisms	Pollution goals in sectoral strategies (agriculture, energy, transport, etc.) Incentives, monitoring systems	Eco-subsidies Pollution Key Performance Indicators in National Strategies	National and regional government / Ministries Environmental protection agencies
EU / International	Ensure coordination, promote equity & innovation	Harmonize policies across Green Deal pillars Fund social-ecological innovation Support EU knowledge hubs	Horizon Projects Zero Pollution Package Pollution tracking tools	European Commission European Parliament & Council of the EU European Environment Agency (EEA)

5. Conclusions

Achieving Zero Pollution requires more than technical innovation or regulatory enforcement; it demands a systematic transformation across all levels of society. The insights drawn from the six experiment streams of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project underscore the importance of coordinated, participatory, and context-sensitive approaches to pollution reduction. A common theme across these streams is the transformative potential of community-based education. While localized initiatives such as Study Circles, Urban Mobility Labs, Circular Economy Hubs or Clean Energy Workshops can support pollution reduction and foster social engagement, their impact often depends on broader structural conditions and long-term institutional support.

However, these bottom-up innovations often face structural barriers, including weak policy integration, fragmented governance and insufficient financial or technical support. Another key insight is the communication gap between pollution science, policy and public understanding. Many promising solutions fail to scale due to limited awareness of the links between daily practices and pollution impacts. Education - both formal and informal - emerges as a critical lever for long-term change, particularly when grounded in lived experience and co-creation. The analysis of policy gaps highlights persistent inconsistencies between environmental ambitions and economic incentives. Subsidies for pollution-intensive sectors, uneven enforcement across EU regions, and limited use of behavioral and social insights continue to hinder progress. Furthermore, marginalized groups - often disproportionately affected by pollution - are not sufficiently protected or empowered by current policy frameworks. To close these gaps, the recommendations emphasize a need for integrated policy design, stronger multilevel governance, and investment in enabling conditions - especially at the local and regional levels. Financial mechanisms, capacity-building, and knowledge-sharing platforms must be expanded to align grassroots innovation with nation and EU-level strategies.

In sum, accelerating transformative change toward a pollution-free Europe depends on coordinated efforts across all levels; from individual behavior and local experimentation to structural reform and international alignment. Embedding equity, participation and systems thinking at the base of pollution governance will be crucial for achieving the EU's Zero Pollution vision by 2050. The social experiments conducted within the six thematic streams of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project have at least taken the first practical step in this direction and, together with local partners, have begun to pave the way for a more sustainable future.

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Appendix

Table A1.1. Social experiments profiles.

#	Priority area (thematic stream)	Approach	Target group	Place of social experiment	Local partner organisation	Context (rural/urban)*
1	Clean Energy	Community visioning	Policymakers, businesses, local communities	Granada, Spain	Local authority (Diputación de Granada)	mix
				Bełchatów, Poland	NGO (Polish Green Network)	mix
				Jaywick, UK	Local authority (Essex County Council)	rural
				Ærø, Marstal, Denmark	NGO (Fonden Motorfabrikken Marstal and Blue Innovators)	rural
2	Circular Economy	Local accelerator hubs	Local businesses, academics, authorities, and NGOs	Santo Tirso, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Santo Tirso)	urban
				Val-de-Marne, France	NGO (Val de Marne en Transition)	urban
				Nicosia/Limassol/Larnaca, Cyprus	National authority (Cyprus Organization for Standardization)	mix
				Ljubljana, Slovenia	Local authority (Technology Park Ljubljana)	urban
3	Efficient Renovations	Knowledge networks on energy renovation and eco-home-tours	Under-represented and marginalised groups and renovation professionals (40-60% women)	Zaragoza, Spain	NGO (ECODES Zaragoza)	urban
				Nógrád County, Hungary	NGO (Habitat for Humanity Hungary)	rural
				Vilnius, Lithuania	Local authority (Let's Renovate the City Vilnius)	urban
				Louisburgh, Mayo County, Ireland	Regional authority (Mayo County Council Louisburgh)	rural
4	Sustainable Mobility	School mobility labs	Per experiment 30 young people (aged 10-16) and 5 to 10 stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and school administrators	Braga, Portugal	Local authority (Municipality of Braga)	urban
				Galway, Ireland	NGO (Am Meitheal Rothar Ireland)	urban
				Panevėžys, Lithuania	NGO (ECAT Lithuania)	urban
				Sofia, Bulgaria	NGO (Sofia Development Association Bulgaria)	urban
5	Sustainable Food	Local food Assemblies	Young people aged 18-35 years	Stockholm, Sweden	NGO (REFORMATEN)	urban
				Cella Monte, Italy	NGO (ASFODELO)	rural
				Košice, Slovakia	NGO (Klíma ťa potrebuje)	mix
				Wageningen, Netherlands	NGO (Gemeente Wageningen)	mix
6	Preserving Biodiversity	Study Circles	Diverse group of 10-15 adults per Study Circle (ensure diversity in age, gender, occupation and social vulnerability)	Tolmin, Slovenia	NGO (Posoški razvojni center)	rural
				Amaroussion, Greece	Local authority (Municipality of Amaroussion)	urban
				Kilfinane, Ireland	NGO (Ballyhoura Development CLG)	rural
				Stockholm, Sweden	Local authority (Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm)	urban

*Note: Rural/urban is based on [European Commission \(2014\), A harmonised definition of Cities and Rural Areas: The new Degree of Urbanisation.](#)

Table A1.2. Overview of data sources that fed into the D5.2 Climate Action & Zero Pollution reports.

#	Data source / Reference	Description / Comment
1	Ruiz, H., Katusic, V., Hamika S., 2025. Implementing Local Accelerator Hubs to foster business innovation in the circular economy. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270150 . <i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i>	This report builds on the insights from the social experiments in Portugal, Cyprus, Slovenia, and France. The report presents key recommendations for enhancing the circular economy by developing local accelerator hubs (LAHs) to promote business innovation and improved knowledge dissemination, ecosystem development, regulatory support, and multi-stakeholder collaboration for local organizations.
2	Gray, E. K., Rohse, M., Fahy, F., Jost, C., 2025. Community visioning for just, clean energy futures in Europe. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270128 . <i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i>	This report explores community visioning's potential as a tool for stakeholder engagement in energy decision-making based on examples from social experiments in four sites: Belchatów, Poland; the province of Granada, Spain; Jaywick, Essex County, the United Kingdom; and the island of Ærø, Denmark. Recommendations for policy makers to enhance participation in energy transitions are provided.
3	Foulds, C., Royston, S., Crowther, A., Aggeli, A., Robison, R., Noreña Ospina, M., Wieser, P., 2025. Bringing together citizens and professionals to develop know-how for energy efficient renovations. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270137 . <i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i>	This report outlines the design and implementation of Knowledge Networks that bring together professionals and citizens to share knowledge about renovations. We recommend a Knowledge Network approach to policyworkers and practitioners as an effective tool in the delivery of the Renovations Wave and other energy efficiency goals. Based on four Social Experiments, delivered in Hungary, Lithuania, Ireland and Spain, several recommendations for policy makers are provided.
4	Šmid Hribar, M., Ribeiro, D., Strasser, S., Paliogiannis, H., 2025. Exploring the Study Circle approach in fostering change in biodiversity values among adults. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270156 . <i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i>	This report presents insights from non-formal community learning, using a study circle approach, that was applied in social experiments related to preserving biodiversity in Tolmin (Slovenia), Athens (Greece), Stockholm (Sweden) and Ballyhoura (Ireland). It reflects on citizen participation and collaborative community projects for biodiversity protection and how these can strengthen policy and decision-making.

5	<p>Beers, P.J., van Bellen, L., Carraca, J., Girardi, A., Gritti, V., Hebinck, A., Kiewik, J., Mourato, J., Nieboer, S., Silvestri, G., Truninger, M., 2025. Scaling food systems transitions. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369887</p> <p><i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i></p>	<p>This report presents insights from four social experiments in Italy, Slovakia, Sweden and Netherlands, with agricultural-oriented local partners who carried out a transition arena process to create a local food transition narrative. The local-specific transition narrative and associated action agenda, as well as impediments on meso-level are identified, and recommendations for policy makers provided.</p>
6	<p>Haufe, N., Tönkö, A., 2025. Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315291</p> <p><i>(and internal Appendices A+B)</i></p>	<p>This report presents insights from social experiments Braga (Portugal), Galway (Ireland), Panevezys (Lithuania), and Sofia (Bulgaria) based on local urban mobility labs in schools in order to enhance sustainable school travel.</p>
7	<p>Kovács, K., et al., 2024. SHARED GREEN DEAL Case Study Guides. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL</p>	<p>This publication provides an overview of the design and implementation of social experiments in the six Green Deal priority topics (Circular Economy, Clean Energy, Efficient Renovations; Preserving Biodiversity, Sustainable Food, Sustainable Mobility, with a concise and accessible overview of key insights from these social experiments and emphasis on practical takeaways.</p>
8	<p>Urios, J., Fasert, C., Gore, T., Foulds, C., Afghani, N. 2022. Behavioural, Cultural and Social issues in EU Green Deal policy documents. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL.</p>	<p>This report sets out the policy context for the SHARED GREEN DEAL project by providing an overview of the most relevant EU policy documents for the project's research agenda. It assesses the extent to which these documents present insights into behavioural, social, and cultural issues drawn from SSH disciplines, in identifying drivers of and/or barriers to successful policy implementation and propose interventions for successful policy implementation.</p>

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